

THE ROLE OF THE HEMIS INFORMATION SYSTEM IN MODERNIZING THE HIGHER EDUCATION SYSTEM AND ITS FUNCTION IN DESIGNING INDIVIDUAL EDUCATIONAL TRAJECTORIES

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Abstract. *This article explores the role of the Higher Education Management Information System (HEMIS) in the modernization of Uzbekistan's higher education system and its critical function in designing individual educational trajectories (IETs) for students. The HEMIS platform is part of Uzbekistan's ongoing education reforms aimed at enhancing administrative efficiency, transparency, and data-driven decision-making across universities. Key features of the system, such as centralized data management, academic performance tracking, course registration, and resource management, are discussed. Additionally, the article highlights how HEMIS supports students in navigating the credit-module system, personalizing their educational pathways, and providing flexibility through real-time progress monitoring and personalized academic recommendations. The article concludes that HEMIS significantly contributes to creating a more individualized, flexible, and student-centered higher education system in Uzbekistan.*

Keywords: *HEMIS, higher education, Uzbekistan, educational reform, credit-module system, individual educational trajectory, academic performance, student-centered learning, digital education management, educational flexibility.*

In the Republic of Uzbekistan, the "Higher Education Management Information System (HEMIS)" is a complex digital platform introduced within the framework of ongoing reforms aimed at modernizing and improving the quality of higher education management. Currently, more than 226 higher education institutions and over 1 million users are utilizing the system [10]. HEMIS has transformed the operational methods of educational institutions by integrating information management processes, reducing administrative inefficiencies, and ensuring transparency between higher and vocational education. Furthermore, hundreds of other information systems have been integrated with HEMIS.

In this article, we aim to explore the main functions, advantages, and the role of the HEMIS system in the design of students' individual educational trajectories.

Main Functions of the HEMIS Information System

Centralized Data Management: HEMIS integrates information related to students, faculty, and administrative processes into a single platform. This includes personal student information, academic records, attendance, assessments, financial aid details, and more. It allows easy access to data for both administrative staff and students, reducing paperwork and making processes more efficient.

Academic Performance Tracking: One of the main functions of HEMIS is to track students' academic performance. The system automatically collects and organizes information on student grades, course completions, credits earned, and overall academic standing. This tracking ability is invaluable for both students and faculty as it helps monitor educational progress in real-time.

Course Registration and Management: Students can use HEMIS to register for courses, track prerequisites, and manage their academic schedules. This process is streamlined, making it easier for students to plan their semester based on course availability, credits, and academic needs.

Attendance and Behavior Monitoring: HEMIS helps institutions monitor student attendance and engagement in their courses. Faculty can upload attendance data, and students are notified in real-time about any potential issues regarding missed classes or low participation.

Resource Management: For universities, HEMIS also serves as a financial management tool. It helps institutions manage budgets, track spending on resources such as libraries, research, and infrastructure, and ensures efficient use of funds. This capability is important for government oversight, providing transparency in how universities allocate their resources.

Communication Between Stakeholders: HEMIS facilitates improved communication between students, faculty, administrative staff, and the Ministry of Higher Education. It enables the government to monitor and control higher education processes accordingly. Meanwhile, students and faculty have digital means to resolve administrative issues and access important information in real-time.

Regulatory Compliance: The platform ensures that universities comply with national education standards and internal policies. It generates reports for the Ministry of Higher and Secondary Specialized Education, providing insights into institutional performance, graduation rates, faculty qualifications, and other critical metrics.

Advantages of HEMIS in Higher Education

Increased Transparency and Accountability: HEMIS fosters a culture of transparency by making student records and institutional data accessible to all stakeholders. This reduces the risk of data manipulation and ensures that educational processes are more accountable.

Improved Decision-Making: The analytics tools within HEMIS allow for data-driven decision-making. University administrators can monitor student outcomes, identify trends, and make informed decisions regarding curriculum adjustments, faculty workloads, and resource allocation. For the Ministry of Education, HEMIS provides real-time insights that guide policy decisions aimed at improving the national higher education system.

Reduced Administrative Burden: By automating many administrative processes, HEMIS reduces the workload on university staff, allowing them to focus more on core educational tasks. Tasks such as grading, tracking student performance, and managing course enrollments are handled more efficiently through the platform.

Empowering Students: The system empowers students by giving them greater control over their educational data and academic paths. Students can view their progress, manage their course loads, and receive personalized guidance, all through a user-friendly digital interface.

Role of HEMIS in Designing Individual Educational Trajectories

One of the most transformative aspects of HEMIS is its role in supporting the design of individual educational trajectories (IETs) for students. This function is particularly important within the context of Uzbekistan's credit-module system, where students have greater flexibility in customizing their learning pathways based on their academic interests, career goals, and pace of learning. Here's how HEMIS facilitates this:

Integration with the Credit-Module System: HEMIS is compatible with Uzbekistan's credit-module education system, where students accumulate credits through the completion of courses and modules. The system helps students track their earned credits and understand what courses they need to take next to complete their programs. It also enables students to choose electives that align with their career aspirations and personal interests, allowing for a more customized learning experience.

Advising and Recommendations: The system can generate personalized academic recommendations for students based on their past performance, current standing, and future goals. Advisors can use the platform to guide students in selecting courses that match their skills and interests, facilitating the creation of an individual educational trajectory tailored to each student's needs.

Progress Monitoring and Adjustments: By providing detailed academic progress reports, HEMIS helps both students and advisors monitor how well a student is progressing along their individual educational trajectory. If a student is struggling in a particular subject or falling behind on their credits, the system allows for timely interventions. Students can adjust their course load or modify their academic plans in response to this feedback.

Expanded Student Independence: The platform gives students greater independence in managing their educational paths. With real-time access to their academic data, students can plan ahead, adjust their schedules, and make informed decisions about their academic journey. HEMIS also allows students to explore various learning opportunities, such as internships, research projects, or additional certifications, that may complement their chosen trajectory.

Flexible Learning Paths: HEMIS enables universities to offer a more flexible and individualized approach to education, especially useful for non-traditional students, such as those balancing work and studies. With access to their educational data, students can spread their courses over a longer time frame, taking advantage of part-time or distance learning options.

Data-Driven Personalization: HEMIS employs data analytics to track student performance across various courses and modules. Based on this data, the system can highlight areas where students may need additional support or suggest alternative paths that better align with their strengths. This creates a more personalized and supportive educational environment.

In conclusion, the HEMIS platform is a key tool in Uzbekistan's efforts to reform and modernize its higher education system. Its benefits go beyond administrative efficiency, offering

enhanced transparency, accountability, and data-driven decision-making. Importantly, its role in designing students' individual educational trajectories is pivotal to creating a more personalized, flexible, and student-centered education system. By integrating tools that support the credit-module system, advising, and progress monitoring, HEMIS empowers students to take control of their academic paths and achieve their educational goals more effectively.

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